

Shake table test of scaled gymnasium frame with cylindrical arch roof – characteristics of seismic response

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Abstract

In this research series, shake table experiments have been conducted on 1/4-scale school gymnasium frame with cylindrical lattice arch roof supported by single-story substructures with response control devices as friction damper braces and tuned mass dampers (TMDs) at E-Defense, a full-scale 3D shake table test facility, and their seismic response characteristics, response reduction effects by damping devices, and collapse mechanism under severe seismic inputs are confirmed. This paper reports the basic information of the test setups and their seismic response characteristics confirmed by shake table tests, compared with the previous response evaluation methods proposed based on analyses in the past.

Keywords: Latticed shell arch, Gymnasium, Seismic response, Shake table test, E-Defense

1. Introduction

Seismic response of raised latticed shell roofs with supporting substructures are characterized by the predominance of complex vibration modes in which the roof responds in the vertical direction even under horizontal seismic input, and the response is also excited by the period and mass ratio of the supporting substructure. In earthquake-prone countries such as Japan and China, numerous studies on the seismic response characteristics of lattice roof structures have been conducted, and the equivalent static seismic load distribution has been vigorously proposed to simplify the design using static analysis. Some of them have been published in "AIJ Recommendation for Design of Latticed Shell Roof Structures (2017)", "IASS Guide to Earthquake Response Evaluation of Metal Roof Spatial Structures (2019)" and so on. However, there have been very few experiments confirming these response characteristics with realistic frames using shake table facilities. In this background, in 2023, shake table experiments were conducted on 1/4-scale school gymnasium frame with cylindrical lattice arch roof supported by single-story substructures with response control devices as friction damper braces and tuned mass dampers (TMDs) at E-Defense, a full-scale 3D shake table test facility in Japan, and their seismic response characteristics, response reduction effects by damping devices, and collapse mechanism under severe seismic inputs are confirmed. This paper reports the basic information of the test setups and their seismic response characteristics confirmed by shake table tests, compared with the previous response evaluation methods proposed based on analyses in the past.

Figure 1 Testing set-up

Photo 1 Overview of testing set-up
Table 1 Member specification

Member	Section	Steel	A (mm ²)	I (mm ⁴)	Z (mm ³)
Column	□-100×50×2.3	STKR400	655.2	848000	17000
Beam (weak axis)	□-150×100×3.2	STKR400	1533	2620000	52500
Roof arch	□-50×50×3.2	STKR400	572.7	204000	8160
Roof beam	CT-75×75×5×7	SS400	892.5	426000	7460
Roof brace (weak axis)	+75×66×4.5×6	SS400	720	109000	3690
Tie beam (weak axis)	[-150×75×6.5×10	SS400	2371	1170000	22400
Friction damper brace	H-150×100×6×9	SS400	2635	10000000	135000

Figure 2 Measurement plan

2. Test setup

Figure 1 shows the experimental system and Photo 1 shows the actual setup view. The experimental system consists of a full-scale 3D vibration table, a test specimen, and a collapse prevention jig. The experiment was conducted at E-Defense, a full-scale 3D seismic test facility in Miki City, Hyogo Prefecture, Japan, owned by the National Research Institute for Earth Science and Disaster Resilience (NIED).

As shown in Figure 1, the test specimen was a 1/4-scale model of a cylindrical roof arch with a supporting substructure (beam-to-beam span: 6.0 m, girder span: 8.0 m, roof top height: 3.2 m), assuming a steel roof gymnasium with RC substructures of an elementary or junior high school consisting of an arena section only. However, the member cross-sections and connection details were

designed with priority given to the experimental purpose of confirming the roof collapse behavior. Each member section is shown in Table 1.

Figure 2 shows the measurement plan. The items measured were displacement relative to the shake table (transverse direction of the support frame and vertical direction of the roof frame), absolute acceleration (transverse and vertical direction of the shake table, supporting girder line and vertical direction of the roof frame), surface strain of the members of each part of the specimen, axial force, shear force, and bending moment of the support frame columns, axial force, shear force, and bending moment of the roof arch members, axial force of the roof horizontal braces, axial force of the friction damper brace bolts introduced, axial force and axial displacement of the friction damper braces. Displacement is measured with a laser displacement meter, acceleration with a servo accelerometer, and surface strain with a strain gauges. The axial force introduced into the bolt of the friction damper is measured by a strain gage-converting load cell. The axial force and bending moment of the member force are calculated by multiplying the measured values of the strain gages by the nominal values of the cross-sectional area and cross-sectional coefficient. Especially for the friction damper brace, the axial strain was separated by the 4-gauge method and measured by increasing the output. A total of 281 measurements (45 acceleration, 28 displacements, 204 strain, and 4 load cells) were taken at a sampling frequency of 1 kHz using a dynamic logger owned by the experimental facility.

Shaking protocol and seismic input wave are shown in Table 2 and Figure 3, respectively. The input seismic wave was the observed data of the main shock of the 2016 Kumamoto earthquake wave (April 16) spectrally fitted to the Japanese building code spectrum and the time axis was reduced by 1/2 to consider the scale law keeping the acceleration ratio as 1.0, and the amplitude magnification factor was defined as 100%.

Table 2 Input shaking menu (1-1 to 1-4)

Test No.	Input waves (input frequency or level)	PGA (m/s^2)	Condition of specimen
1-1	Sweep wave (0.1~10 Hz)	0.6	Friction damper: fixed Roof sectional defect: reinforced
1-2	Seismic wave (50%)	1.9	
1-3	Seismic wave (100%)	4.0	
1-4	Sine wave (4.92 Hz)	0.8	

Figure 3 Input seismic wave (Kumamoto, horizontal)

3. Vibration modes

Figure 4 compares the experimental results of the transfer function at each measurement point of the roof frame under the sweep wave input (Test No. 1-1) with the approximate curves obtained by the experimental modal analysis. As shown in Figure 4, the approximate curve of the transfer function estimated by the experimental modal analysis corresponds to the peak of the smoothed transfer function, indicating that the dominant natural frequency characteristics are captured with sufficient accuracy. As shown in Figure 5(a) and (b) and Table 3, the first-order mode (0.21s, damping ratio about 1.7%) and the fifth-order mode (0.13s, damping ratio about 1.4%) are found to be the dominant natural vibration modes of the cylindrical arch roof with single-layer supporting substructure for the transverse direction input. As shown in Fig. 6, the first-order mode corresponds to the inversely

Figure 4 Comparisons of transfer function between experimental and estimated value (No.1-1)

Table 3 Predominant modal characteristics under elastic response

Mode No.	Natural frequency F (Hz)	Natural period T (s)	Damping factor h (%)	Effective mass ratio M_e/M_R (%)
1	4.86	0.206	1.7	31.42
3	6.06	0.165	0.6	0.01
5	7.61	0.131	1.4	19.96
6	7.90	0.127	0.8	6.93

Figure 5 Predominant modal shapes of elastic response

symmetric one-wave mode in which each arch vibrates independently. In addition, as shown in Figure 5(c), the fifth-order modes are considered to contribute mainly to the horizontal response of the entire building to the transverse inputs, based on the Y1 axis transfer function, which bears most of the horizontal stiffness in the transverse direction of the support structure.

As shown in Table 3, the experimental modal damping ratio of about 1.7% is smaller than the initial structural damping of 2% used in the dynamic analysis of steel structures. This 2% is a conventional damping ratio that takes into account the damping caused by friction between the structural frame of the building and the finishing materials or between the finishing materials, and the experimental modal damping ratio is considered to be the result of removing the effect of this friction. Most of this approximately 1.7% was due to the friction of the reinforcing cover plate at the edge of the roof arch material. On the other hand, although the third- and sixth-order mode damping ratios are smaller than

those of the first- and fifth-order modes, their effective mass ratios are also smaller, and their influence on the seismic response of the roof structure is negligible.

4. Seismic response

The correspondence between the equivalent static seismic load and the elastic roof response acceleration is verified. The equivalent static seismic load of the cylindrical arch roof for the transverse direction input is calculated based on the horizontal acceleration A_{eq} at the supporting substructure eave height RFL, the period ratio of the entire building to the roof structure R_T , the mass ratio of the roof section to the entire building R_M , the roof response amplification factor F_H and F_V depending on the roof half-subtended angle θ (rad.). The nodal acceleration coordinate functions A_H and A_V are evaluated as equations (1)~(4), which simulate the roof section inverse symmetric one-wave mode. Equations (5),(6) are used for F_H' and F_V' in the range of $R_M > 1.2$ and $R_T < 1$, $R_M > 1.2$ and $R_T < 1.5$, considering the resonance effects between the roof and the substructure.

$$A_H(x, y) = A_{eq} \{1 + (F_H - 1) \cos \pi(x / L_x)\} \quad (1)$$

$$A_V(x, y) = A_{eq} F_V \sin \pi(2x / L_x) \quad (2)$$

$$F_H = \begin{cases} 3/2 & (0 < R_T \leq 1/4) \\ 1/2(\sqrt{1/R_T} + 1) & (1/4 < R_T \leq 1) \\ 1 & (1 < R_T) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$F_V = \begin{cases} 3C_V\theta & (0 < R_T \leq 5/16) \\ (\sqrt{5/R_T} - 1)C_V\theta & (5/16 < R_T \leq 5) \\ 0 & (5 < R_T) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$F_H' = \sqrt{F_H^2 + 1 / \{(1 - R_T^2)^2 + (1 / R_M)^\theta\}} \quad (5)$$

$$F_V' = \sqrt{F_V^2 + 1 / \{(1 - R_T^2)^2 + (1 / R_M)\}} \quad (6)$$

Here, the nodal coordinates are set at the origin in the center of the roof section, the constant C_V in equation (4) is 1.33, and the half-subtended angle θ of the roof section is $\pi/6$ rad.

Table 4 shows the calculated equivalent static seismic loads based on the experimental results, Table 5 and Figure 7 shows the ratio of the horizontal and vertical roof peak seismic response values from the a experiment (actual roof response amplification factors F_{RH} and F_{RV}) to the horizontal accelerations A_{eq} and A_{eq} at the eave height of the support structure. Here, three options of evaluating A_{eq} as shown in Figure 6 are compared. Here, the horizontal acceleration A_{eq} at the roof supporting level RFL is evaluated as the average value of A_{eq1} (red line) from the accelerometer records between Y1 and Y5, A_{eq2} (blue line) calculated from the analyses assuming the roof as a rigid body.

Table 4 Factors of equivalent static seismic load

T_R	T_S	R_T	R_M	F_H	F_V
0.206 s	0.019 s	0.09	2.08	1.68	2.24

Table 5 Comparisons of response amplification ratio

A_{eq}	Input	F_{RH}	F_{RV}	F_{RH}/F_H	F_{RV}/F_V
A_{eq1}	50%	1.37	2.64	0.81	1.17
	100%	1.37	2.46	0.81	1.10
A_{eq2}	50%	2.02	3.90	1.20	1.74
	100%	2.24	4.01	1.33	1.79
A_{eq3}	50%	1.52	2.94	0.90	1.31
	100%	1.58	2.84	0.94	1.26

Figure 6 Three options for evaluating A_{eq}

Figure 7 Comparisons of roof response acceleration between evaluated and experimental values (No. 1-2 and No. 1-3)

A_{eq3} (green line) is evaluated from CQC analyses, with the vibration modes above 90% of the sum of effective mass ratios, with damping ratio of 1.67%. As shown in Table 5 and Figure 7, the equivalent static seismic loads obtained by applying the experimental results of A_{eq1} correspond well with the experimental results of the response acceleration distribution of the roof ridge, indicating its validity as a load distribution. As shown in Table 5, the actual roof response amplification factors, F_{RH} and F_{RV} , calculated from the experimental results of A_{eq1} also correspond to the roof response amplification factor evaluation equations (3)~(6) within 20% error. On the other hand, as shown in the comparison between A_{eq2} , the equivalent static seismic load assuming the roof as a rigid body, underestimates the experimental results and the error in the roof response amplification factor is also large. Evaluation of the roof accelerations using A_{eq3} showing the improved accuracies, which indicates that the correct evaluation of A_{eq} reflecting the effect of roof response is important.

4. Conclusions

The conclusions obtained within the scope of this study can be summarized as follows

- 1) The damping ratio of the specimen frame without finishings obtained from the elastic response of the experiments was about 1.7%, which includes the effects of joints friction.
- 2) The seismic response of the cylindrical roof arch during elastic response to transverse inputs was dominated by the asymmetric one-wave vibration mode for the entire roof structure and the asymmetric one-wave mode of individual roof arch.
- 3) The equivalent static seismic loads at the roof obtained by applying the experimental values of the transverse direction input A_{eq} at the roof supporting level roughly correspond to the response acceleration obtained from the shake table tests. For evaluating A_{eq} , it is important to use the correct values reflecting the effect of roof responses.

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